

used for pH measurements. All measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. $4.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ stock solution of TPO (B.D.H. indicator) was prepared in double distilled water.

Spectral data and pH measurement :

A series of solutions of TPO were prepared by placing 5 ml aliquot of the freshly prepared stock solution in 25 ml volumetric flasks and adding calculated amount of acid or base to get the desired pH, and then making up the volume with distilled water. The pH of each solution was finally measured and the spectral curves for each solution were determined over the entire visible region. The graphical presentation of the pH-spectral data is shown in Fig. 1 which reveals that the region of maximum absorption of TPO lies at 380 and 430 nm. The dissociation constants of TPO at these wavelengths are calculated by using the following equations :

$$K = \frac{A_m - A_a}{A_b - A_m} [H^+] \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{or } -\log K = -\log[H^+] - \log \frac{A_m - A_a}{A_b - A_m} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{hence } pK = pH - \log R ; R = \frac{A_m - A_a}{A_b - A_m} \quad \dots (3)$$

where A_m , A_a and A_b are total molar absorbance of the mixture of the two forms of TPO, absorbance of one form at lower pH and absorbance of the other form at higher pH, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constants of TPO were calculated from several selected points obtained by drawing curves between pH and absorbance at 380 and 430 nm using equation 3. A_m values were approximately the arithmetical mean of the limiting values of A_a and A_b . To obtain the best apparent values of K , the entire absorbance-pH curves should be constructed and the pH at which the second derivation in equation 3 becomes zero be determined, at which $pK = pH$. However, we have found out values of R at different pH values from the data presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS TPO AT 380 nm AND 430 nm

pH	A_a { 380 nm : 0.750 430 nm : 0.475		A_b { 380 nm : 0.500 430 nm : 1.415	
	380 nm	430 nm	380 nm	430 nm
5.20	0.725	0.510	6.16	6.61
5.80	0.700	0.770	6.40	6.14
6.60	0.600	1.120	6.47	6.26
7.00	0.550	1.240	6.40	6.36
8.00	0.515	1.385	6.80	6.52

Overall pK_1 value at 380 nm and 430 nm—6.42.

Using similar data of A_m , A_a and A_b between pH 11.60-13.20, the overall pK_2 values at 380 and 430 nm are calculated and found to be 12.50.

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Ferric Chloride Catalysis in the Bromination of Anisole by Br_2 in 97% Aqueous Acetic Acid

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It is a common practice in synthetic organic chemistry to speed up the halogenation of aromatic compounds by the addition of halogen carriers such as iodine, iron powder, anhydrous halides of iron, zinc and aluminium, silver salts and pyridine¹⁻⁴. In anhydrous acetic acid, $FeCl_3$, $ZnCl_2$ and IBr were found to be good catalysts for the bromination of acetanilide⁵.

In the presence of IBr , $ZnCl_2$ and $NaCl$ as catalysts, the bromination of anisole in 85% aq. HOAc had been shown⁶ to proceed by simultaneous catalysed and uncatalysed processes. In the present investigation⁷ the catalytic role of anhydrous $FeCl_3$ in the bromination of anisole was examined.

Experimental

The reaction was studied at 303 K by mixing 5 ml each of anisole (0.001 M) and bromine (0.001 M) with/without anhydrous $FeCl_3$ in 97% aq. HOAc, allowing them to react for definite intervals of time and arresting the reaction by the addition of 10 ml aq. solution of KI containing NaF (5 g NaF in 150 ml 10% KI), which prevents the oxidation of KI by Fe^{3+} by complexing with the latter.

In the absence of any catalyst, the anisole (0.001 M) and bromine (0.001 M) reaction is of the second order. When the concentration of $FeCl_3$ in the reaction mixture is increased (from 0.002 to 0.013 M) there was a steady increase (from 0.62 to $1.5 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) in the observed k_2 (Table 1).

The rate equation for the $FeCl_3$ -catalysis may be represented as follows :

$$-d[Br_2]/dt = k[C_6H_5OCH_3][Br_2] + k_0[C_6H_5OCH_3][Br_2][FeCl_3]^n \quad \dots (1)$$

$$k_2 = k + k_0[FeCl_3]^n \quad \dots (2)$$

where k_2 is the observed second order rate constant, k and k_0 are the rate constants for uncatalysed and

TABLE 1—CATALYSIS BY FeCl₃ IN ANISOLE-BROMINE REACTION

[Anisole]=[Bromine]=0.001 M Solvent : 97% aq. HOAc (v/v)
Temp. : 308K

FeCl ₃ M	[FeCl ₃]/[Br ₂]	k ₂ (1 mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	$\frac{k_2 \text{ catalysed}}{k_2 \text{ uncatalysed}}$
0	0	0.44	—
0.002	2	0.62	1.4
0.004	4	0.75	1.7
0.006	6	0.81	1.8
0.008	8	1.1	2.5
0.010	10	1.4	3.2
0.018	18	1.5	3.4

catalysed reactions, respectively and n the order for FeCl₃.

For n equal to 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0, k₂ vs [FeCl₃]ⁿ was plotted. The plot was linear only when n was equal to 1, (Fig. 1) showing that FeCl₃ order is one. The intercept and the slope gave 0.44 l mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹ and 85.7 l² mol⁻² sec⁻¹ for k and k₂, respectively.

Fig. 1. FeCl₃-catalysis in the bromination of anisole in 97% aq. HOAc.

Discussion

The catalytic role of FeCl₃ can be explained by the mechanisms A and B.

In mechanism A, anisole and bromine form a transition state in which a polarised and partially weakened bromine molecule is attached to the p-position of anisole. The FeCl₃ molecule removes Br⁻ as FeCl₃Br⁻ giving σ-complex, which rapidly loses a proton to give the product (p-bromoanisole).

Mechanism A : FeCl₃-catalysis in anisole-Br₂ reaction.

Mechanism B : FeCl₃-catalysis in anisole-Br₂ reaction.

In mechanism B, the ion-pair containing Br⁺ is first formed from Br₂ and FeCl₃. This being a good electrophile attacks anisole to form a σ-complex, which by a quick proton-loss forms the product.

Conclusion :

In mechanism A, FeCl₃ plays a secondary role, viz., removal of Br⁻ from the transition state. But, in mechanism B, FeCl₃ has a major role, that of forming the electrophile itself. Kinetically, these two mechanisms cannot be distinguished. Both will explain the observed first order each for anisole, Br₂ and FeCl₃.

Thus, FeCl₃ is a mild halogen carrier for the bromination of anisole in 97% aq. HOAc.

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